

Supplementary Material

- **Sensor responses:**

Figures S1-S4 illustrate the signals acquired from the sensory perception systems (eNose1 (TGS822), eNose2, eTongue, and eEyes) for detecting herbal teas. The following graphs were done by using a few sensors of each device.

Figure S1. eNose1 response obtained from measurement # 2 reference TGS 822 gas sensor.

Figure S2. eNose2 response obtained from measurement # 2 through the MQ135 gas sensor.

Figure S3. eEyes: Herbal Teas. Measurements #2, NIRONE Sensor S2.0-REFL/S2.0-SMA.

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Figure S4. eTongue: Herbal Teas. Measurements #2, Measurements #2, Carbon electrode AC1 101 R2.

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• Data classification using LDA method in each device:

Figures S5-S6 show the signals acquired from the sensory perception systems for detecting herbal teas. The following graphs were done by using each device in order to see the capabilities to classify the categories.

Figure S5. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eNose1 system.

Figure S6. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eNose2 system.

Figure S7. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eTongue system.

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Figure S8. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eEyes system.

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• **PCA and LDA analysis using Data Fusion:**

Figures S9-S16 show the plots obtained of the information extracted from each device, where the data combination of the devices was used with the PCA and LDA algorithms.

Figure S9. PCA plot to discriminate the herbal teas through the eNose1, eTongue and eEyes systems.

Figure S10. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eNose1, eTongue and eEyes systems.

Figure S11. PCA plot to discriminate the herbal teas through the eNose2, eTongue and eEyes systems.

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Figure S12. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eNose2, eTongue and eEyes systems.

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Figure S13. PCA plot to discriminate the herbal teas through the eTongue and eEyes systems.

Figure S14. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eNose2, eTongue and eEyes systems.

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Figure S15. PCA plot to discriminate the herbal teas through the eNose1, eNose2. eTongue and eEyes systems.

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Figure S16. LDA plot to classify the herbal teas through the eNose1, eNose2. eTongue and eEyes systems.

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